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Incorporation of Agroforestry Tree Species on Agricultural Systems' Gain: Synthesis Study

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Abstract: Most rural areas in African countries have soil and land management issues, which result in crop failure, fodder shortages, and a lack of basics for agricultural product outputs. Furthermore, loss of soil fertility and climate variability make it impossible to achieve enough crop yields and livestock production year after year, resulting in poor food security. Agroforestry projects involve the planting of trees on farmland with the goal of increasing the contribution of the tree crop component and the overall productivity of the farming system. As a result, increasing agricultural production and productivity requires the use of low-cost, long-term soil fertility and fodder supply management strategies. Furthermore, the goal of this synthesis is to emphasize the importance of tree components in the implementation of farming systems. Where these do not exist, however, screening prospective tree species and developing innovations tailored to specific conditions is critical. Finally, research on agroforestry trees requires a long-term, mid-term, and short-term investment strategy.

Keywords: Adoption, Biomass, Climate, Farmland, Fertility, Inorganic, Smallholder, Yields

Introduction

Inorganic fertilizer has been utilized in modern agriculture since the green revolution era and has considerably enhanced productivity and production (Ahmad and Anjum, 2020). The small share of the global market is due to declining soil fertility, low application rates, unfavorable input-output price ratios, and market development constraints (Ariga and Jayne 2009; Shaha *et al.*, 2014; Kakar *et al.*, 2020). However, Ariga and Jayne (2011) in SSA countries, like most other parts of the world, rely on international markets for fertilizers because domestic production is limited and reliant on a state-run plant that requires major repairs and upgrades.

Inorganic fertilizers have been used in commercial, emergent, and subsistence farming to grow crops (Vance *et al.*, 2000; Fox *et al.*, 2007; Ding *et al.*, 2016). This is due to the fact that inorganic fertilizers are simple to use, quickly absorbed, and utilized by plants. However, if not used properly, it might have a negative impact on the soil's health or quality (Ahmad and Anjum 2020). As a result, uncontrolled use of inorganic fertilizer could deplete nutrients and acidify the soil, resulting in a reduction in soil fertility (Satyanarayana *et al.*, 2002; Khan *et al.*, 2018). The use of inorganic fertilizers raises production costs, resulting in lower profits in crop production businesses (Khan *et al.*, 2018; Rahman and Zhang 2018). As a result, the majority of smallholder farmers in agricultural and livestock production are resource constrained, unable to purchase inorganic fertilizers in sufficient quantities to support plant growth during its growing season (Myeni *et al.*, 2019). Inorganic fertilizers have become extremely expensive and scarce as a result of rising energy costs, particularly in Sub-Saharan African countries.

The scarcity of inorganic fertilizer among smallholder farmers has piqued their attention. Several governments in Sub-Saharan African countries (SSA) have made attempts to support local and regional manufacturing in order to enhance access to inorganic fertilizers (Muzari *et al.*, 2012; Sheahan and Barrett 2017). This has the potential to boost smallholder agricultural productivity while saving money on foreign currencies and avoiding price swings on the international market.

It is generally recognized that minerals derived from the soil nutrient pool have a significant impact on agricultural performance. As a result, nutrient deficiencies in the soil, such as calcium, phosphorus, nitrogen, and potassium, have a negative impact on crop development (Rahman and Zhang, 2018).

According to Mercer and Pattanayak (1999), Ajayi *et al.* (2011), and Mafongoya *et al.* (2006), new agricultural methods have been proposed to address the cost of inorganic fertilizers and their negative environmental consequences. As a result, it is critical to address the fact that infertile soils and a changing climate make it impossible to achieve sufficient agricultural yields year after year, putting food security in jeopardy (Chavula and Hassen, 2022). The loss of soil quality due to erosion and nutrient depletion due to insufficient nutrient supply and maintenance is a prevalent problem (Dao and Cavigelli, 2003; Patel *et al.*, 2001; Mishra and Patel, 2009). As a result, introducing newly developed technology for boosting soil fertility while minimizing damage to the ecosystem is a top concern (Kaczan *et al.*, 2013; Gitz *et al.*, 2016).

Agroforestry is one of the latest agriculture technologies that has been adopted to improve soil fertility and agro-ecological sanity (Mubiru 2019; Chavula and Hassen, 2022). Agroforestry is defined in so many different ways by scholars 'spatial combination of tree components on farmland with animals and crops.' Agroforestry is a collective name for land-use systems and technologies where woody perennials such as trees, shrubs, palms, bamboos are deliberately used on the same piece of land management unit as crops or animals either in some form of spatial arrangement or temporal sequence (Leakey, 2014). There are both ecological and economic linkages between the many components of agroforestry systems (Sileshi *et al.*, 2014).

Agroforestry's goal is to provide meaningful ecological and economic interactions between trees and agricultural components (Akinnifesi *et al.*, 2011; Xu *et al.*, 2019). Many experts have studied agroforestry approaches for decades and subsequently distributed

them to smallholder farmers in rural areas across most African countries (Franzel *et al* n.d.; Jama and Zeila, 2005; Franzel *et al.*, 2014).

Agroforestry, according to Leakey(2014), presents several chances to improve food output and productivity through nitrogen-fixing plants and shrubs. When compared to natural fallowing, agroforestry technologies like enhanced fallows return soil fertility faster (Phiri *et al.*, 2003 Mafongoya *et al.*, 2003; Akinnifesi *et al.*, 2008). A rotational system that uses selected nitrogen-fixing tree species as fallow species instead of natural vegetation in rotation with cultivated crops is known as an enhanced fallow (Deans *et al.*, 2003; Phiri *et al.*, 2003). For instance, deliberately scattered trees on croplands *Faidherbia albida*, *Sesbania sesban* and/or *Leucaena leucocephala* enhance soil nutrition. Alleys of "*Gliricidia sepium* reduces crop failure on a cultivated yield. Furthermore, agroforestry multipurpose tree species are known to provide fruits for human consumption, fuelwood for energy and fodder trees for energy (Akinnifesi *et al.*, 2006). The goal of agroforestry practices, according to Ajayi *et al.* (2007), is to improve sustainable soil management and poverty alleviation in rural areas.

Agroforestry tree species are known to provide a diversity of benefits on farmland (1) supporting services (2) provision services and (3) regulation services. Agroforestry multipurpose tree species can reclaim the degraded soils. To reduce shocks, provide a folder for animals and/or livestock. It also boosts soil organic matter, which has the ability to improve soil structure and microbial activity (Love *et al.*, 2006; Kharhu *et al.*, 2011). Through leaf biomass, the trees provide a huge surface area for improving water retention and soil nutrient retention (Fargione *et al* 2009). Soil organic matter promotes moisture and nutrient retention, as well as the physical qualities of the soil (Barral *et al.*, 1998; Allan, 2005).

The use of inorganic fertilizers in excess has a negative impact on soil quality. Furthermore, fertilizer is costly, so long-term viability is unlikely, particularly for smallholder farmers (Mwangi, 1996; Zhen *et al.*, 2005). As a result, the introduction of low-

cost soil fertilizing options is critical to improving agricultural production. However, the influence of affordable, available, better sustainable ways (most convenient methods) that smallholder farmers can utilize in their fields to boost crop and animal output is compounded in this synthesis study.

Discussion

Definition of terms

Coppicing: Trees should be cut down to the ground level to encourage regrowth from the stumps that remain (Pyttel *et al.*, 2013; Vyamana *et al.*, 2021).

Deep capture: The extraction of nutrients from soil depths beyond the reach of crop roots by tree roots (Sileshi *et al.*, 2014).

Pollarding: With the goal of extracting wood and browse, producing regrowth beyond the reach of animals, or lowering the shadow created by the crown, a tree's crown is cut down while the main trunk is left (Hartel *et al.*, 2017).

Protein (fodder) bank: Plantings of trees or shrubs in a farm or pasture area to provide livestock with a supplemental source of protein-rich fodder (Sileshi *et al.*, 2014).

Silvopastoral: Trees are an important feature of pastureland in this land use system (Aryal *et al.*, 2019).

Smallholder farmers: A smallholder farmer is typically thought of as someone who farms a tiny plot of land, planting food crops and perhaps small variety of income crops (Altieri *et al.*, 2012).

Soil: the layer(s) of loose mineral and/or organic material at/near the planetary surface that is impacted by physical, chemical, and/or biological processes and usually holds liquids, gases, and biota and supports plants" (FAO, 2018).

Fodder: farm animals' food something or someone that is exclusively beneficial for a specific purpose (Sileshi *et al.*, 2014).

Soil nutrients: Some soil nutrients, such as nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), sulfur (S), magnesium (Mg), and calcium (Ca), are essential components of organic compounds in plants, such as proteins and nucleic acids, or help to regulate cellular pH and osmotic potential internally (Igwe, 2005; Zafar *et al.*, n.d.).

Overview of Agroforestry

Smallholder farmers who can't afford or get regular supplies of inorganic fertilizers turn to organic sources of nutrition. Leaf biomass as a crop fertilizer: Multipurpose tree species aid in soil fertility development by providing above and below-ground biomass; diverse forms of leaves, roots, and twigs cover soil, cushion soil from heavy rains, minimize erosion, enhance water holding capacity once mixed, and improve nutrients status (Sayer 2006; Datta and Singh 2007; Singh *et al.*, 2020).

Nitrogen fixation is the major nutrient requirement; it is scarce in the soil, abundant in the atmosphere, and captured by fertilizer trees through nitrogen fixation (Vance *et al.*, 2000; Sileshi *et al.*, 2014; Chavula and Hassen, 2022). The breakdown of plant shedding nodules provides nitrogen. Multipurpose tree species aid in nutrient mining by allowing access to nutrients that are normally leached beyond the rooting zone of agricultural crops (Srinivasarao *et al.*, 2014). For example, in *Sesbania sesban*, nutrients are delivered to the top layer and mineralization happens at various rates of releasing nutrients to the soil. Soil structure is usually improved by opening up the soil and enabling water to infiltrate. Through root penetration, multipurpose tree species open the soil, allowing for the growth of soil fauna as well as other biological activity. In conclusion, multipurpose tree species improve soils by fixing carbon through photosynthesis, then litter carbon, and below decay, legumes fix nitrogen, nutrients uptake from weathered rocks, and nutrients from their leaves. Additionally trap nitrogen from the atmosphere, and legumes fix nitrogen, nutrients uptake from weathered rocks, and nutrients from their leaves can trap nitrogen from the atmosphere (Nygren *et al.*, 2000).

Empirical Evidence

Makangango *et al.* (2020) investigated the biomass output and nutritional content of three agroforestry tree species growing on an acid Anthropic Ferralsol with recurrent harvesting at different cutting heights in the field (*i.e.* to encourage coppicing). Smallholder farmers may benefit from agroforestry systems, which can assist them overcome difficulties including soil deterioration and low livestock production. The study looked at the impact of different cutting heights (0.3m- 1.0m) and repeated harvests (1m–5m) on biomass production and chemical composition of the leguminous trees *Acacia angustissima*, *Leucaena pallida*, and *Mimosa scabrella* Anthropic Ferralsol in Southern Rwanda. *M. scabrella* had the most crude protein (CP) and *A. angustissima* had the least, whereas *M. scabrella* had the most neutral detergent fiber (NDF) and acid detergent fiber (ADF). Despite the fact that all species produced high CP content feed at all cutting heights, *A. angustissima* and *L. pallida* should be cut at a lower cutting height (0.3 m) for better overall quality and biomass output. Makangango *et al.* (2020) concluded that the tree species are a vital incorporation on farmland as they consist elements needed for livestock production. On the other side, the tree species also have a huge capacity to reclaim degraded soils.

Tefera *et al.* (2019) investigated the potential of agroforestry for carbon sequestration as a means of mitigating climate change. Agroforestry is a one-of-a-kind, large-scale operation that combines woody plants with crop and animal components. As a result, the function of agroforestry in climate change mitigation has gotten a lot of attention in recent decades. As a result, the most important contribution of agroforestry in terms of climate change is in reducing carbon dioxide emissions by sequestering carbon from the atmosphere. This because agroforestry offers a higher potential for increasing carbon sequestration in mostly agriculture-dominated settings than monocrop agriculture (Tefera *et al.*, 2019).

Oyebamiji *et al.* (2017) investigated the effect of agroforestry tree leaf biomass transfer with nitrogen fertilizer on maize stover yield in Makera, Nigeria. The key strategies

for nutrient enrichment, particularly nitrogen enrichment, are the cultivation of leguminous tree crops and biomass transfer, which can also be employed as an organic fertilizer source. The study looked at the influence of urea on leafy biomass transfer from leguminous agroforestry trees *Albizia lebbeck* and *Parkia biglobosa* on maize stover yield. According to the data, *Albizia lebbeck* leafy biomass alone boosted stover output. Nonetheless, the addition of 120 kg N ha⁻¹ urea to the EVAT in 2009 resulted in improved stover output (Oyebamiji *et al.*, 2017). As a result, amending the soil with *Albizia lebbeck* biomass and up to 40 kg N ha⁻¹ urea enhanced soil quality and increased stover yields.

The argument that agroforestry is a second soil fertility paradigm was addressed by Mango and Hebinck (2016) in a case study of soil fertility management in Western Kenya. However, there is no simple answer to this question. As a result, agroforestry has been promoted in Western Kenya through various programs and organizations since the early 1990s as an alternate technique for replenishing soil fertility. These practices coexist with enhanced fallows and mutually modify one another through a variety of interactions on the farm and in villages, as well as with technical institutions (Mango and Hebinck, 2016). Agroforestry system represent a range of soil fertility alternatives that correspond to the various nutrient and other soil conservation needs. Farmers' livelihoods will benefit from low-cost methods for providing nutrients to crops on a large scale. Scientists realized that cutting the cost of restoring fertility is critical for the region's and the world's agricultural futures.

Sileshi *et al.* (2014) suggested the diversification of agro-ecosystems with fertilizer trees can optimize indigenous soil nitrogen supply and increase the productivity of the land. Fertilizer trees also ensure multifunctional agriculture by providing timber, fodder, shade, soil enhancement, and watershed management, among other benefits. Fertilizer trees, unlike synthetic nitrogen sources, ensure more internal nutrient recycling and water availability, resulting in improved nutrient efficiency. As a result, by reducing external inputs, notably nitrogen fertilizers, enhancing resource and land-use efficiency, and delaying erosion, they can make a significant contribution to sustainable agriculture.

Although the adoption of fertilizer trees in many parts of the world has been slower than expected, there have been remarkable triumphs in others. Local tradition, economic concerns, and land ownership have all influenced the adoption of fertilizer trees in traditional production systems (Sileshi *et al.*, 2014). These conventional systems are deteriorating and losing productivity, but they may serve as a model for new land management approaches in which fertilizer trees play a larger role in promoting food, forage, and fiber production.

Also, the study by Quinion *et al.* (2010) on fertilizer tree technologies such as intercropping, relay cropping, improved fallows and biomass transfer. The study found that tree technologies promote sustainable agriculture, low-input alternatives to inorganic fertilizers, and complementary inputs to inorganic fertilizers among smallholder farmers in Malawi. According to Quinion *et al.* (2010), the research further explored the ability of technology to help rural families of smallholder farmers improve their food security and livelihoods in two areas of Malawi. The size of the landholdings influences the technologies chosen, and large landholdings are connected with more benefits. Despite the fact that, according to Quinion *et al.* (2010), fertilizer tree technologies on agriculture lead to a reduction in hunger months and poverty alleviation over time. Thus, the inability to achieve livelihood security, absorb and cope with shocks, and improve overall welfare drives the adoption of technologies at the household level.

According to Kalaba *et al.* (2010) research on the role of agroforestry in improving biodiversity and livelihoods in rural communities in Southern Africa Better agroforestry systems (AFS), such as increased fallows that resemble shifting farming and other AFS, benefit rural livelihoods, improved socioeconomic position, and land-use system ecological functioning. The study aimed at solving biodiversity and socioeconomic challenges by domesticating a variety of priority indigenous fruit tree species and evaluating soil fertility replenishing agroforestry systems on farmland or in communities. In comparison to subsistence agriculture, AFS adds value by creating monetary income through the sale of a variety of products (Kalaba *et al.*, 2010). The report used information from research

undertaken in southern Africa over the last two decades to determine the role of natural forest resources and AFS in improving the socio-economic livelihoods of smallholder farmers and promoting biodiversity conservation.

Pandey and Rai (2007) obtained similar results when the time of application of *Gliricidia sepium* leaf biomass on maize production was assessed to determine the decomposition and release of nitrogen from leaves, soil nitrogen mineralization, nitrogen uptake, shoot biomass and grain yield of the crop. The findings of the experiment indicated that the rate of soil nitrogen mineralization, nitrogen uptake, shoot biomass and grain yield in maize were highest in the treatment i.e. where leaf biomass was applied two weeks after sowing and in which leaf biomass was incorporated four weeks after sowing the yield was the lowest. Maximum 50% nitrogen was released quickly from the leaves within 15 days and the remaining 48%-49% gradually in 60 days. Pandey and Rai (2007) added on to say that though large quantities of nitrogen can be harvested in the form of leaves, nitrogen recovery rate by the associated crops was found rather low in the range of 10-20%. One of the reasons for such low values might be lack of synchrony between nitrogen demand by the crop and nitrogen release from the leaves, synchrony between the nitrogen release and its uptake by the crop depends upon decomposition pattern, which in turn is influenced by the quality of the leaves, and time of its application. Hence, what is attributed to this finding, the other reason which could result in low production in the treatment of *Gliricidia sepium* leaf biomass (Pandey and Rai, 2007; Pandey *et al.*, 2007).

Therefore, furthermore, Pandey and Rai (2007), study concluded that *Gliricidia sepium* leaf biomass decompose quickly and releases maximum nitrogen within 15 days and the remaining part in two months. Nevertheless, in the experiment, *Brassica oleracea* was transplanted after leaf biomass has been decomposing for 14 days hence there was a little mismatch between the nitrogen demands of the crop. Whereas, Masinde and Omolo (2007) experimented in Kenya to assess the impact of the biomass of sun hemp, cowpeas and delichos on cabbage, the experiment of these three legumes was laid out in factorial design during long rains. After the harvest of legumes, cabbage was grown during short

rains/under irrigation. The results indicated a low yield of cabbage when no legume was used. The results indicated that the *Gliricidia sepium* leaf biomass transfer technology could be used as an alternative to inorganic fertilizers for vegetable production among vegetable producers.

Mafongoya *et al.* (1997) farmers in parts of Southern Africa were collecting leaf litter from Miombo woodlands as a source of nutrients for their crops. On the other side, because it enhanced soil quality, leaf litter proved to be a sustainable farming strategy. Smallholder farmers who embraced the approach saw an increase in farmland productivity. As a result of a more cost-effective agricultural production method, household income increased with guaranteed sustainability. On the other hand, regular tree cutting for foliage had a negative impact on the conservation of Miombo or any other forest. This could be a viable substitute for inorganic fertilizer.

Gachengo (1996) found that *Tithonia diversifolia* green biomass transferred into a field was quite effective in supplying nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium to maize, equivalent to the amount of commercial NPK fertilizer recommended. Gachengo (1996) went on to say that in some cases, maize yields were higher with tithonia biomass than with inorganic fertilizer. According to Ademiluyi and Omotoso (2007), and Jama *et al.* (2000) a trial that was carried out to examine the effect of fresh *T. diversifolia* biomass versus inorganic fertilizer on maize yields. The investigation found that maize grown without any input (control) yielded the lowest yield of 0.8t grain/ha. Tithonia biomass increased maize output by 58 percent over control, whereas chemical fertilizer increased maize yield by 63 percent above control. This means that the impacts of tithonia and chemical fertilizer on yields were not significantly different. The experiment concluded that leaf biomass could be used in maize production, as the yield did not differ. The Tithonia tree species can easily grow and establish on a farmland.

Conclusion

Finally, the synthesis study demonstrates that tree components are critical to a farming system's success. As a result, smallholder farmers can afford to plant agroforestry tree species on their farms, which are easy to grow and can be planted from cuttings or seeds. The transmission of information to farmers through the findings provided can affect adoption and utilization of this technology. Agroforestry tree species have many benefits for any farming system and help to encourage long-term development. Climate change adaptation, resilience, and mitigation activities are also aided by agroforestry tree species technology. Agroforestry multipurpose tree species technology must be driven in least developed countries, particularly in Sub-Sahara Africa, in order to achieve three climate-smart agriculture objectives. Finally, fertilizer tree species are critical in restoring deteriorated and depleted soil quality. Provide feed for cattle and building stakes, on the other hand.

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